

Pázmány Péter Catholic University
Faculty of Information Technology and Bionics

MSc Thesis

Improving Laser Speckle Imaging Technology

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Info-Bionics Engineering MSc

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Thesis Proposal Form

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Thesis

Title: Improving Laser Speckle Imaging Technology

Summary of the thesis:

Laser Speckle Imaging is an optical monitoring technique for motion-related events. Laser Speckles form from the superposition of scattered coherent light resulting in interference patterns. Any change in scatterers, typically movement, changes the pattern as well. At Institute for Computer Science and Control, the student is conducting experiments aiming to improve the technique, especially Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging (LSCI). It measures movement by calculating a contrast map on a digital image or sequence of images, usually from normalizing the variance of intensity by the mean intensity in local spatial, temporal or spatio-temporal windows. As such, LSCI is most often used for flowmetry. The student is aiming to improve the dynamic range, sensitivity and granularity. A sample in the loop type system is also being developed.

Detailed task description:

- The student should help creating a camera system for Laser Speckle Imaging.
- The student should help creating a laser driver.
- The student should create a microfluidic phantom for flowmetry and system evaluation.
- The student should take part in conducting ex vivo and in vivo flowmetry experiments.
- The student should take part in researching and developing the imaging system for Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging.
- The student should implement and develop software on an embedded device for a sample in the loop system.

Date: Budapest, 23 March 2021

Hereby I apply for the approval of the topic of my thesis.

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The student has regularly attended consultation sessions, and has met all the requirements of the task description. The thesis work meets the formal and content requirements described by the Annex 1 of the Education and Exam Policy (EEP).

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Master Thesis Declaration of Authenticity

I, undersigned Imre Gergely Jánoki, student of the Faculty of Information Technology and Bionics at the Pázmány Péter Catholic University, hereby certify that this thesis was written without any unauthorized help, solely by me and I used only the referenced sources. Every part, which is quoted exactly or in a paraphrased manner, is indicated clearly with a reference. I have not submitted this thesis anywhere else.

Imre Gergely Jánoki

Abstract

I work at the Institute for Computer Science and Control (SZTAKI), where my research group recently started to explore the field of laser speckle imaging with a focus on improving Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging (LSCI). The method is based on the laser speckle phenomenon, which is in fact the interference pattern of backscattered coherent light. With a stable laser light source, the pattern does not change in the presence of only non-moving, static scatterers. However, moving, dynamic scatterers cause fluctuations in the interference pattern that is picked up by a camera as intensity changes. This variation over the exposure time appears as a blurring effect. The contrast is calculated as the standard deviation divided by the mean of pixel intensities in a small – usually 3-11 pixels neighbour – sliding window.

The speed of movement – usually named the flow rate in practical applications — is inversely proportional to the decorrelation time τ_c , and the autocorrelation function of the electric field depends on it. LSCI methods map the relative flow rates to the calculated contrast map utilizing the blurring effect introduced by the decorrelation over the exposure of the image. Absolute flow rates are roughly estimated with the addition of calibration methods and using the most recent descriptions of said complex relation. Research in the field aims to improve the mapping by new processing methods and technical solutions as well as trying to better approximate the exact relation of decorrelation time and contrast. During my thesis work, our group has published^{1,2} and submitted³ three scientific articles on the subject, of which I am a co-author. Most of my work and results are included in the articles.

In my MSc thesis I introduce the literature and related works of laser speckle imaging outlining the underlying physics and the mathematics behind. I also show its relevance and a compilation of applications. Some of the recent advancements are presented as well.

¹M. Siket, I. Jánoki, K. Demeter, M. Szabó, and P. Földesy, “Time varied illumination laser speckle contrast imaging”, *Optics Letters*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 713–716, Feb. 2021.

²P. Földesy, M. Siket, I. Jánoki, K. Demeter, and Á. Nagy, “Ensemble averaging laser speckle contrast imaging: Statistical model of improvement as function of static scatterers”, *Optics Express*, vol. 29, no. 18, pp. 29 366–29 377, Aug. 2021.

³M. Siket, I. Jánoki, and P. Földesy, “Sample-in-the-loop laser speckle contrast imaging” *Submitted to Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, 2021.

I present my work and our solutions to three problems in the methodology and results. First, our new method called **Time Varied Illumination Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging** (TVI-LSCI) is discussed, which extends the dynamic range of measurable flow rates during a single exposure by using offline optimized varying intensity illumination. We also proposed a technical implementation scheme that uses pulse modulation to emulate the intensity modulation. I show the results of the ex vivo and in vivo experiments. Second, our **Sample-in-the-Loop** feedback-based online continuous wave illumination LSCI and TVI-LSCI optimization and measurement approach is presented with its hardware and software implementation. I also give the results of exemplary experiments in three different optimization scenarios. Lastly, I introduce **LSCI ensemble averaging** using interframe decorrelated illumination and our technical implementation using one static and one rotating diffuser. We proposed a model and validated it on ex vivo measurements. Exemplary ex vivo and in vivo experiments were also conducted.

During my thesis work, I researched the related literature. I took active part in designing and building our different measurement systems. I developed a microfluidic channel slide phantom for system evaluation. I took active part in researching and developing the theory and implementations of three LSCI improvement methods. I took a major role in the development of our sample-in-the-loop system for an embedded device. I helped organizing and I conducted a number of ex vivo and in vivo flowmetry experiments.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

I work at the Computational Optical Sensing and Processing Laboratory at the Institute for Computer Science and Control (SZTAKI). Among the many other smaller and bigger projects, we are doing research on Laser Speckle Imaging, which I chose to be my thesis work. The goal of the research is to improve existing methods and to move towards the development of future commercial solutions.

Our group in the laboratory mainly focuses on research in the field of computer vision that is connected to healthcare. The most widely used Laser Speckle technique in medicine is the Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging (LSCI). It is an optical method for flowmetry, mostly used for monitoring disease induced blood flow changes in the microcirculation at various areas [1]. As such, I worked specifically on improving LSCI. During my work, I helped exploring the limitations [2] and problems of the technique.

First, I took part in creating an easily portable Laser Speckle Imaging system connected to a computer. It has an optimally focused laser diode with a thermoelectric-cooled mount and a camera with optics on a precisely adjustable stage.

I was actively part of developing a novel method: Time Varied Illumination Speckle Contrast Imaging (TVI-LSCI). It increases the dynamic range of the flow rate covered in a single exposure by an order of magnitude compared to constant illumination methods. I helped formulating the theory behind. I built the ex vivo experimental setup and arranged the in vivo experiments. I took part in writing the scientific research article about the method that was published in Optica (formerly OSA) Publishing's Optics Letters [3].

I designed a laser driver to create the desired laser pulsetrains for the experiments with TVI-LSCI. I made a CircuitMaker printed circuit board design for it.

I designed a microfluidic device for flowmetry and system evaluation, and ran simulations for verification. We use these PDMS-on-glass fabricated devices in most of our ex vivo experiments.

I took part in creating an embedded Sample-in-the-Loop system. I built the hardware setup and I took a major part in the implementation and development of the software environment. We have submitted a scientific article about the method and details of the system [4].

I helped investigating the theory behind ensemble averaging for Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging. I planned the ex vivo and in vivo experiments and took part in them as well. I took part in writing the scientific research article about the statistical model of the method that was published in Optica (formerly OSA) Publishing's Optics Express [5].

1.2. Structure of the Master's Thesis

The structure of this Master's Thesis is as follows:

Related Works In this chapter first I describe what the laser speckle phenomenon is. Then I present a compilation of applications and the relevance of laser speckle imaging in medical flowmetry. I introduce laser speckle contrast imaging, the main topic of my thesis work, including the basic calculations and the most important advancements of the technology.

Methodology I describe the three main problems me and my research group tried to solve. First, I present the theory and mathematical background behind the dynamic range extension method of time varied illumination laser speckle contrast imaging we described. I also present the practical implementation we proposed, the numerical simulation, and the measurement system I helped to build. I describe the protocols and setups of the ex vivo and in vivo measurements I helped to organize and took part in.

Second, I present the setup I improved for our Sample-in-the-Loop online optimization approach for time varied illumination laser speckle contrast imaging. I describe the idea and operation procedure of the method and its three optimization scenarios. I also give details about the channel slide design I developed for evaluation.

Finally, I present the theory, mathematical background behind and the model identification process of the effect of ensemble averaging for laser speckle contrast imaging my research group constructed and described. I present our implementation of decorrelated

illumination using a static and a rotating diffuser I helped to build and evaluate, and a method to apply for temporal speckle contrast imaging I proposed.

Results First, I present the results of model identification and the process of the offline optimization of time varied illumination. I present the results of our ex vivo and in vivo experiments.

Next, I detail the software of Sample-in-the-Loop Laser Speckle Imaging, in the development of which I took a major part. Then I give the results of exemplary measurements in the three optimization scenarios.

Lastly, I present the three experiment we conducted using ensemble averaging, and the related validation process.

Conclusion I detail and evaluate the tasks performed and compare them to the set objectives.

2. Related works

2.1. Laser Speckle Imaging

The laboratory did not conduct research and experiments involving Laser Speckle Imaging before. My supervisor was curious about it and had an idea of improving the technology. Once he realized, that it is an important and relevant topic that also fits well into our research field and profile, the laboratory agreed in doing research with Laser Speckle Imaging. As a first step, I had to research the literature about it, and soon we turned our focus on Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging.

2.1.1 The Laser Speckle Phenomenon

Laser Speckle Imaging is a non-invasive or minimally invasive full field optical method that is used to measure the movement of particle-like scatterers. A wide-field of rough surface or most often scattering particles are illuminated by a coherent light source. The interference created from the superposition of the scattering coherent light results in the laser speckle pattern that is captured by the digital camera sensors. At first glance this image is similar to a dense salt and pepper noise. If there are only static scatterers, the speckle pattern is static as well. However, when the scattering particles are moving, the interference are changing as well, as phase-changes of light occur, which manifests in intensity variations picked up by the sensor.

2.1.2 Applications

The first application of Laser Speckle Imaging (LSI) was described in [6]. The authors proposed a simple method for measuring the velocity distribution of the flow field. They selected a sufficiently short enough exposure time for a single photo, that the blurring effect of the variation of speckle intensity appears on the image. The varying contrast on the image was visualized to give a picture of the velocity distribution in the flow field. They also examined the potential application on mapping the retinal blood flow, and conducted an early stage experiment.

However, the field of application is wide as many showed it ever since. With the technical advancements of digital camera sensors and fast and cheap computers, the research field of laser speckle imaging has expanded hugely. In the medical field, LSI can

be used for the flowmetry of microcirculation and blood perfusion. Beside the previously proposed retinal blood flow imaging [7], [8] used it to access the vessel structure and the relative cerebral blood flow velocity through an intact rat skull. [9] developed a dual-display laparoscopic laser speckle contrast imaging system for minimally invasive surgeries, especially for gastrointestinal surgeries. They could image relative flow fields in rat and swine bowels as well with a working laparoscope tip distance of 1-5 cm . To study changes in microvasculature flow and architecture of rodent dorsal skin fold model in vivo that was caused by external stimuli, [10] proposed the use of LSI. [11] demonstrated an LSI-based strategy for accurate assessment of skin burn severity. [12] found that laser speckle contrast imaging is a reliable technique for assessment of microcirculation in people with diabetic foot ulcers.

Not only blood flow, but biological activity can also be measured with LSI, commonly named biospeckle. [13] evaluated frozen semen kinetics of bovine species, and compared the results of biospeckle with the traditional light microscopy-based analysis. They found that biospeckle could be a reliable tool in sperm cell fertility investigation at artificial insemination centres. The assessment of product and food quality is a very important task in agriculture. One of the early uses was the identification of fungi contamination in seeds, like beans [14] [15]. For certain fungi, bioactivity was significantly higher than in the control group. This activity can be numerically measured, and it can be visualized on pseudocolor images using biospeckle. The possibility for post-harvest monitoring of tomato ripening was also evaluated with positive results [16]. [17] applied biospeckle to oranges, and used various classifiers including artificial neural networks to assess the chilling and freezing of the fruits. According to [18], identification of the bruising of apples can be determined early, as bruised areas show lower biospeckle activity. Additionally, [19] used biospeckle for the detection of endophytic fungi colonization of leaves of *Jatropha curcas*. Water transportation in the venation of leaves was observed similarly to blood flow in microcirculation, and at the same time, the difference in bioactivity between infected and non-infected leaves was shown.

2.1.3 Relevance of the Technique in Medical Flowmetry

Although there are other existing methods for blood flow imaging, but they come with different drawbacks. Laser Doppler Imaging has a low temporal resolution that comes from its mechanical scanning [20]. Doppler Optical Coherence Tomography (Doppler OCT) is widely used in velocimetry, angiogram and elastography. It has a good depth

resolution, which LSI lacks. However, simultaneous high temporal resolution and high spatial resolution with a wide field is hard to achieve with Doppler OCT [21]. In comparison, the advantages of LSI include not only its high simultaneous temporal and spatial resolution, but its low cost and ease of implementation.

2.2. Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging

There are many LSI-based analyzing techniques. Most of them measures activity as the correlation of irradiance as a function of time. Of these, actual activity maps can be acquired using Fujii's method [22], and the Generalized Difference method [23] and its derivatives. Currently, the most widely used technique for flowmetry is Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging (LSCI).

2.2.1 Calculation

The basis of the LSCI method is to create a mapping between flow rates and contrast. For this, a spatial sliding window is used. In this window, the standard deviance of the intensity is calculated and then it is normalized by the mean intensity. This spatial speckle contrast κ is defined as:

$$\kappa_s = \frac{\sigma(I_s)}{\langle I_s \rangle}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $\sigma(I_s)$ is the standard deviation, and $\langle I_s \rangle$ is the sample mean, both are defined over a small spatial neighborhood of $n_s \times n_s$ pixel intensity values. A basic requirement for LSCI is that the minimum speckle size should exceed the Nyquist criterion in order to maximize the contrast of the speckle pattern [24]. For subjective speckle patterns, such as that recorded with a digital camera, the speckle-size S can be estimated using the Airy disk formula:

$$S \approx 2 \times 1.22\lambda(1 + M)f/D, \quad (2.2)$$

where λ is the laser illumination wavelength, M is the magnification of the imaging system, f is focal length and D is the aperture diameter, or rather (f/D) is the f-number of the system. This is often overlooked, however - despite failing to fulfill this requirement - the resulting contrast maps will still map the flow rates proportionally. The spatial neighborhood should be small to have as good spatial resolution as possible, however it should be chosen to be larger than the speckle-size, and so n_s is typically

set from 3 to 11. Eq. (2.1) maps the relative flow speeds: with a higher flow rate the decorrelation increases. Faster flows appear more blurry over a single image, and so κ is smaller there, and vica versa. [25] presented the normalized second order model of the underlying physics as:

$$v_2(T) = \frac{\beta}{T^2} \int_0^T \int_0^T \rho |g_1^n(t'-t'')|^2 + (1-\rho) |g_1^n(t'-t'')| dt' dt'', \quad (2.3)$$

where v_2 is the reduced second moment, T is the exposure time, ρ is the fraction of dynamic and total scatterers, $(1-\rho)$ is the fraction of static and total scatterers, and $t'-t''$ gives the time differences during the exposure. β is a normalization factor. This constant eliminates the effect, where the perceived contrast of the intensity levels are reduced as the ratio of detector size to speckle size increases.

g_1 is the autocorrelation of the electric field [6] that was corrected in [26]:

$$g_1^n(t) = \exp(-(t/\tau_c)^n), \quad (2.4)$$

where τ_c is the correlation time. The value of n depends on the second type of dynamics. For single scattering unordered motion (SU) and multiple scattering ordered motion regime (MO) $n = 1$, which represents small vessels in the size range of ≈ 30 to $150 \mu\text{m}$. $n = 2$ describes single scattering from ordered motion for larger vessels (SO). Surprisingly, multiple scattering unordered motion (MU) describes the dynamics capillary perfused tissue (i.e. parenchyma and small visible vessels) $n = 0.5$. Some regions are best fit with mixed dynamics ($g_1^{0.5}, g_1^1, g_1^2$), for example SO is found in the center of large vessels but it may transition to SU/MO on the outer regions of the vessel diameter. Blood flow from vessels to parenchyma transitions from SU/MO to MU dynamics, as red blood cells slow down and contribute competitively. These dynamics should be weighted accordingly extending Eq. (2.3). Using these equations, from the calculated speckle contrast Eq. (2.1) we can determine τ_c , and then using $\kappa(T, \tau_c)$ and $\sqrt{v_2(T, \tau_c)}$ equivalency we can identify other parameters.

Speckle contrast calculation and post-processing to estimate the flow rate are heavily affected and have high statistical uncertainty due to this small sample size. Thus, it is common practice to capture a sequence of frames ($n \approx 10-100$), the spatial speckle contrast is calculated separately on each of them and then averaged across the contrast maps gathering information of an $n_s \times n_s \times n$ cuboid.

The other main approach in Laser Speckle Contrast Analysis (LASCA) is to use the temporal statistics first described by [27]. [28] showed that it has a much higher spatial resolution than spatial LSCI, and it can give additional information about blood perfusion changes in small blood vessels. Temporal laser speckle contrast analysis also has an advantage to be nearly independent of the contribution of static scatterers. Spatial and temporal analysis can be combined to create spatiotemporal laser speckle contrast analysis [29]. These temporal methods calculate the first-order statistics of integrated speckles throughout a sequence of images:

$$K_t = \frac{\sigma(I_t)}{\langle I_t \rangle} = \sqrt{\frac{\langle I_t^2 \rangle - \langle I_t \rangle^2}{\langle I_t \rangle^2}}, \quad (2.5)$$

where $\langle I_t \rangle$ are the mean, $\langle I_t^2 \rangle$ are the mean-square values of speckle intensity fluctuations during the fixed time interval t . Similarly to spatial methods, K_t is inversely proportional to the velocity of scatterers [27]. The temporal and spatiotemporal laser speckle contrast analysis methods work on an $n_s \times n_s \times n$ cuboid. n_s is the spatial size of the calculation-window, which is 1 in the case of temporal LASCA. n is the total number of frames that is t divided by the fixed exposure time. However, the precise mapping between the contrast and the relative and, even more so, the absolute flow rate is still being researched, depending on multiple factors [3], [26], [30]–[34].

2.2.2 Advancements

LSCI has been a topic in request in recent years, and as such, it has evolved greatly with many advancements being made. With temporal LASCA, [8] measured blood flow through areas abundant in static scatterers. Multi-exposure Speckle Imaging (MESI) [31] was proposed to increase the sensitivity range of conventional LSCI. A new speckle model was also presented that resulted in a much better accuracy of blood flow mapping, as traditional LSCI underestimates large flow speed changes in blood vessels. The first in vivo measurement [35] demonstrated the improved accuracy of MESI during cerebral blood flow imaging. It also reduced the effect of the time-invariant static scattering from the thinned skull of the cranial window. MESI and its derivatives use multiple consecutive LSCI measurements of the same area with constant intensity illuminations and ensuring that the noise variance is constant, but with different exposure times. The obtained speckle images are then algorithmically evaluated to quantify τ_c over the region of interest (ROI).

MESI is a step in getting closer to reliable absolute flow speed extraction via laser speckle imaging. [36] showed that the problem with spatial averaging of speckles due to their size ratio to the pixel size in cameras [24] corresponds to previous assumptions and it is indeed linear in practice. Various LSCI system calibration and calculation methods were proposed to obtain quantitative flow maps [30], [34]. Recently, [26] proposed Dynamic Light Scattering Imaging, which corrected a long-standing deficiency in LSCI theory [37] and accounts for the difference in correlation decay between vessels of different sizes. Their proposed system allows the measurement of the speckle intensity temporal autocorrelation function over a wide field of view and provides the most accurate model for correlation time estimation, however it requires an expensive high-speed camera.

3. Methodology

3.1. Structure of the Chapter

In this chapter I present the problems we had to solve and the tasks I had to do. For each problem and task I detail the related literature, then the theory and methodology of our solutions. The three main problems are stated below.

3.1.1 Time Varied Illumination LSCI

Both in traditional LSCI and in MESI methods the intensity of laser illumination throughout the measurements is fixed. We investigated the effect of using a varying laser illumination during a single exposure, expecting it to extend the dynamic range of LSCI measurements. First, I detail the theory of time varied illumination during a single exposure LSCI. I describe the mathematical background and the underlying physics model. However, the implementation of a variable intensity continuous illumination is cumbersome, and so we substituted it with a binary level pulse modulation, where the duty cycle (frequency) of a pulsetrain of identical pulses changes over time. This solution lifts the burden of calibrating the non-linear characteristics of analog modulation. I describe the requirements and limitations of pulse modulation as well. We performed numerical simulations as a first means of verification.

Next, I describe the measurement system I helped to build. I present the laser speckle imaging microscope stage and setup. I show the laser driver scheme I helped to create in CircuitMaker, which was eventually changed to an off-the-shelf laser driver. Then I also describe the ex vivo and in vivo experiments we conducted, that I planned and helped to organize. I am a co-author of the released scientific article [3] where we introduced our method Time Varied Illumination Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging (TVI-LSCI), and its experimental and exemplary results.

3.1.2 Sample-in-the-Loop LSCI

Despite we proceeded to worked on Ensemble Averaging LSCI first (see Section 3.1.3), I will introduce our work on Sample-in-the-Loop LSCI before, as it is a more direct continuation of TVI-LSCI. We used pulsetrains of identical pulses in our time varied illumination method. However, the different distributions of illumination pulsetrains

were all the result of either predefined or model-based optimizations. This method is offline, requires an accurate model and multiple measurements during which the sample can change causing potentially false or non-usable results.

These limitations raised the need for a faster, possibly model-free implementation. We conceptualized a Sample-in-the-Loop approach, which is an online, feedback-based optimization manner. I present the setup I made for the measurements. I show the custom microfluidic channel slide that I designed. I also performed a simulation of flow in the channel slide. For the measurements, polydimethylsiloxane-based (PDMS) devices were made of the designs. I detail the software that we developed both for continuous wave (CW) and time varied illumination mode. I describe the three different optimization goals we have implemented for distinct experimental scenarios: contrast setpoint control, sensitivity maximization and dynamic range maximization. I am a co-author of the submitted scientific article [4] where we introduce our method the Sample-in-the-Loop Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging and the exemplary results.

3.1.3 Ensemble Averaging LSCI

Static scatterers are the most common and one of the most relevant artifacts in LSCI. One effect is that they cause granularity in LSCI flow maps. I present our idea of reducing this noise in spatial speckle contrast analysis. Our method uses interframe decorrelated illumination during single-exposure ensemble averaging forcing the granularity caused by static scatterers to smooth out. I describe the theory and proposed statistical model of the effect of ensemble averaging with stable illumination and with interframe decorrelated illumination. We investigated the statistical model of improvement as a function of the ratio of static and dynamic scatterers. I also present the system build for Ensemble Averaging LSCI. I am a co-author of the published scientific article [5] where we introduced the theory and our simulated and experimental results.

3.2. Time Varied Illumination Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging

Previous LSCI methods fixed the laser illumination to a constant intensity. This applies to the standard spatial, temporal and spatiotemporal methods as well as MESI [31] and its variations for which light intensity does not change at least throughout a single exposure. It also applies to the specific case of high-speed multi-exposure laser

speckle contrast imaging [33] where a single-photon avalanche diode (SPAD) array takes a series of single-shot images. This sequence has negligible interframe dead time and it mimics multiple exposures, while a longer integration time is obtained by accumulating these shorter frames increasing the dynamic range. Traditional MESI lacks the temporal resolution for real-time in vivo measurements with a trade off of accuracy and resolution. The new, high-speed single-shot acquisition MESI (sMESI) is faster, it has no readout noise even at lower exposure times due to the usage of SPAD, but it has a low quantum efficiency and requires a more complex post-processing. We investigated, what happens if we use a regular CMOS camera to do a single-exposure, traditional LASCA with varying intensity laser illumination, moreover, with pulse modulation instead of analog intensity modulation.

3.2.1 Intensity Modulation

The varying laser intensity during a single exposure is incorporated to Eq. (2.3) by defining $I(t)$ as time dependent illumination intensity further generalizing it:

$$v_2(T) = \frac{\beta}{\int_0^T \int_0^T I(t')I(t'')dt'dt''} \int_0^T \int_0^T I(t')I(t'')g^{\rho,n}(t'-t'')dt'dt'', \quad (3.1)$$

where $I(t')$ and $I(t'')$ are the laser intensities at sampling time instant t' and t'' . Based on the findings of [26], the relation incorporating the ratio of static and dynamic scatterers and flow dynamics translates to

$$g^{\rho,n}(t'-t'') = \rho|g_1^n(t'-t'')|^2 + (1-\rho)|g_1^n(t'-t'')| \quad (3.2)$$

for scenarios where there is no transition in dynamics, as it is in Eq. (2.3). Eq. (3.1) means that we weight the decorrelation with the intensity levels. This transforms to be dependent on the time lag calculating the correlation function. Performing integration once in Eq. (3.1), we arrive to:

$$v_2(T) = \frac{\beta}{\int_0^T R_{II}(t)dt} \int_0^T R_{II}(t)g^{\rho,n}(t)dt, \quad (3.3)$$

where $R_{II}(t)$ is the autocorrelation of $I(t)$. In previous methods $I(t)$ was selected to be constant further reducing $R_{II}(t)$ and the denominator integral to $(1-t/T)$ and $2/T$ found in the traditional *normalized* second moment [25]: $V_2(T) = \int_0^T 2(1-t/T)[g_1^n(t)]^2 dt/T$. However, using varying intensity instead of a constant intensity illumination combines different correlation time to contrast relations into a single measurement.

In MESI, the exposure times of the consecutive images are gradually increased. The total amount of laser light is held constant in each image by adjusting the amplitude with an acousto-optic modulator [38]. For our method, we proposed that let the brightness be a gradually or continuously decreasing function that is similar to those during MESI exposures, but without the separation in time and the unnecessary interframe time that disturbs the temporal resolution. This way the different τ_c values are observed with $I \propto 1/\tau_c$ intensities during the capture of a single-exposure image acquisition.

3.2.2 Pulse Modulation

Laser speckle imaging requires certain properties of the illumination to be maintained during a single exposure or even during the entire measurement process. That is the coherence length and wavelength of the laser light source should be fixed during the measurement, as well as the noise performance of the imaging device. The laser diode should stay thermally stable to avoid mode hopping and the illumination source should stay physically stable, both to avoid changing the speckle pattern at least during exposure that would raise false flow rates to be mapped. A previous presupposition was that illumination intensity should be fixed during exposure as well, however our method gives valid results when the above mentioned, traditional requirements are met.

However, analog modulation systems to change laser light illumination intensity are usually expensive or limited, e.g. laser current modulation, micro-opto-electro-mechanical systems, micromirror arrays, Bragg cells. Recently, [39] proved the validity of nanosecond pulsed speckle contrast imaging using uniform pulse rate. Hence, we decided to use pulsed speckle contrast imaging, that is the binary intensity modulation of constant intensity and finite pulse width pulsetrains. Using such pulsetrains, two parameters determine intensity over given time-interval: the duty cycle and the pulse width, which could be called the fill factor.

This kind of modulation does not only implements the intensity changes during exposure, but it is cheaper than other methods and at the same time, the calibration of the non-linear characteristics of continuous modulation can be avoided. There are limitations to pulse coding as well. The pulses should have a uniform pulse skew that can be counted for while avoiding transients. The determination of the pulse width is crucial, as if the finite pulse width is close to the correlation time it would distort the temporal averaging. This ratio of pulse width and correlation time is estimated from the frame-rate require-

ments and findings of [26] to be $\tau_c/T > 4$. This means, that measurement with our setup of a typical $T = 5\mu s$ pulse width can capture flows with $\tau_c > 20\mu s$.

3.2.3 Numerical Simulations

As an initial experiment and to have a first glance at the effects of time varied illumination, we preformed a simulation where we compared the continuous wave (CW) illumination with an exposure time of 2 *ms* and our TVI method according to Eq. (3.3). Both simulations were placed into the three different – previously mentioned – non-transition dynamics paradigm, with the parameters described in Table 3.1.

	MU	SU	MO	SO
$\mathbf{n} =$	0.5	1	1	2
$\beta =$	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
$\mathbf{1}-\rho =$	0.2	0	0	0

Table 3.1: Simulation parameters of the different flow dynamics dependent on vessel size: multiple scattering unordered motion (MU), single scattering unordered motion (SU), multiple scattering ordered motion (MO) and single scattering ordered motion (SO) [26]

The results can be seen on Fig. 3.1 a) showing the dynamic range, while Fig. 3.1 b) shows the sensitivity using the different flow dynamics models. The main vessel diameter categories are also shown with different colored background, while the windowed subplots of Fig. 3.1 a) show the illumination intensities over time of the two methods. On Fig. 3.1 b) S_a absolute sensitivity was defined as the sensitivity of v_2 to absolute flow changes [40]. It can be seen, that the near-linear (dynamic) range of CW-LSCI (dotted lines) on the logarithmic scale and the sensitivity of it are both heavily localized to a certain τ_c region – and hence to a certain flow speed range and vessel diameter region. This property demands the change in exposure time (and illumination) to capture other regions – yet again, exclusively. In contrast, TVI-LSCI elongates the range of near-linear characteristics on a logarithmic scale, and consequently flattens the sensitivity as well. As another benefit, it also shifts the dynamic range towards the region of τ_c in large vessels namely to higher blood flow speeds. Based on the result of the simulation, this extended dynamic range covers the physiologically important flow speed range [41], making it possible, to capture and map these flow speed in a single exposure.

Figure 3.1: Continuous wave (dotted lines) and time varied (solid lines) illumination simulation results with respect to the non-transitional flow dynamics. Fig. a) shows image contrast to correlation time relations. The physiological regions and their respective flow dynamics are also marked. The windowed plots show the intensity distribution of illumination types over time. Fig. b) shows the absolute sensitivity to correlation time relations. [3]

3.2.4 Measurement System

After the promising results of the simulations, we decided to conduct experiments. For that, we had to create a measurement system. A traditional LSCI system consists of a microscope-like object glass and spacer tubes, a stable laser illumination light source, and a (digital) camera with precisely adjustable exposure time. First we chose a powerful, single-mode laser diode as our light source (RLD84PZJ2, $\lambda=842$ nm, 220 mW, ROHM Co., Ltd., Japan). Our principles of choice was that the laser should be powerful enough to create a high intensity output and it should be single-mode, as it has a better spatial resolution and better stability. It was also important to use a near-infrared or the lower wavelength infrared laser diode that is best fit for blood flow measurements regarding resolution, penetration depth and reflection wavelength of blood. To thermally stabilize the diode, we placed it in a mount with thermoelectric cooling (TEC) stage (HLD001, Thorlabs, Newton, NJ, USA). The diode with the TEC stage was fixed onto a simple manipulator arm with joints so we could adjust it easily. We chose a high-resolution monochrome digital camera of $3.45 \times 3.45 \mu m^2$ pixel size (Basler acA2040-55um, Basler Vision Technologies, Germany). This industrial camera can be directly connected to a host computer – via its USB 3.0 Micro-B connector – where its many settings can be adjusted in its dedicated software. The camera also comes with a software developer kit. We mounted the camera on another simple manipulator arm with joints. For the image acquisition we used a 10x infinity corrected objective (Thorlabs, Newton, NJ, USA).

The previously described system fulfilled the requirements of a traditional LSCI system. With this system, the visible area was $720 \times 540 \mu m^2$ corresponding to 2048×1536 pixels on the images. The speckle size was estimated based on Eq. (2.2) as $S \approx 2.4(1 + M)\lambda N \approx 49 \mu m$ with magnification $M = 10$ and f-number $N = 2.2$ at wavelength $\lambda = 842 \mu m$ of the setup. The resulting speckle size – considering the physical pixel size – was around 14, thus the speckle contrast calculation did not need further correction [36]. Initial test experiments showed the flaws of this setup. Due to the load of the camera and its objective, the manipulator was hard to set well in a balance. Moreover, it easily picked up vibrations blurring the whole image.

For better measurements, we built a holding stage for the microscope part using compatible platforms, screws and fasteners from Thorlabs. To enable TVI-LSCI, we needed the followings: precise camera timing, a laser driver and a controller to generate and

send the proper waveform through the driver. The Basler camera had a 6-pin Hirose male connector for general purpose input/output (GPIO). We used its direct-coupled GPIO and GPIO ground pins to send the trigger signals for the camera, which had trigger mode set in its software.

At the time we had no laser driver, as so I helped designing one. With the help of my supervisor, I created the design (Fig. 3.2) in CircuitMaker [42] which is a free printed circuit board (PCB designing software by Altium Limited. The design consists of several capacitors to attenuate electric transients. The two voltage regulators (7805 and 78L05) are used to make sure that the incoming voltage levels are stable and there are no fluctuations in it. The Texas Instruments CD401006BPWR is a Schmitt trigger, which is an active comparator circuit with hysteresis. It converts an analog input signal to a digital signal using two different thresholds for rising edges and falling edges. Texas Instruments CD4013BE is a flip-flop used to halve the signal and create a duty cycle with 50 percent on ratio. On the right side of the laser diode is a safety diode. Transistor, as usual, act as switches. Although I designed an actual PCB design as well in CircuitMaker based on the schematics, I built the laser driver on a solderless breadboard, and the PCB was never made.

Figure 3.2: The schematics for the laser driver that I designed.

The camera was connected directly to the host computer for the actual image acquisition, but we needed a controller to trigger the camera precisely and to generate the waveforms for the pulses at the same time. For this, we used a data acquisition card (USB-6211, National Instruments Co., Austin, TX, USA) that was also connected to the host computer and controlled using a simple MATLAB [43] code. Figure 3.3 shows the created TVI-LSCI setup.

Figure 3.3: Schematic of the Time Varied Illumination Speckle Contrast Imaging system. (a) Multichromatic incoherent light (white light) illuminated image of the sample side-wall (left side) and channel area (right side) of the channel slide. (b) Single-mode laser illuminated channel image with blood sample in it and a red box showing the area of contrast calculation.

The verification of the proper timing and the stability for the laser driver output and the camera trigger was done with a digital oscilloscope (DS1022C, Rigol Technologies Inc., China), while the laser diode light emittance and light characteristics was evaluated using a Si fixed gain detector (PDA015A/M, Thorlabs, Newton, NJ, USA) and a spectrometer (AvaSpec-ULS2048 StarLine, Avantes Ltd., The Netherlands).

3.2.5 Ex Vivo Experiments

For the ex vivo experiments, I had to put together a microfluidic setup. I used polymer coverslip μ -Slide I Luer channel slides (ibidi GmbH, Germany) with 5 mm channel width and 0.8 mm channel heights. These channel slides are the most simple ones having only a single, straight channel between a single inlet and outlet. The inlet was connected

through Luer adapters and tubes to a syringe in a medical syringe pump (SN-50F6, Sino Medical-Device Technology Co., Ltd., China) that controlled the flow in the channel slide. The outlet was connected to a drainage leading to a waste reservoir. During the initial experiments such as the verification of the system, we used dry yeast granulate mixed in water which has similar size particles to red blood cells. Later we used a 10% emulsion of phospholipid stabilized soybean oil (SMOFlipid lipid emulsion, Fresenius Kabi AB, Uppsala, Sweden) that is often used as a body fluid model in laser speckle imaging research [44].

I organized and took part in the followup ex vivo experiments. We measured room-temperature anticoagulated (citrate) packed red blood cell product for transfusions in a similar manner to the previous ex vivo measurements. The experiment took place in a controlled medical environment at Semmelweis University under the supervision of a medical doctor. The syringe pump has a flow control range from 0 to 600 mL/min , which translates to from 0 to 37.5 mm/s velocities taking into account the volume of the channel slide. We divided this range as a logarithmic distribution of 19 steps to get our measurement points, where the minimum step-size was the resolution of the syringe pump 0.1 mL/min . The imaged area was 720x540 μm^2 of the channel slide with both the channel sidewall and channel being in the field of view. Once we conducted the experiment, postprocessing and evaluation was done in MATLAB. For the contrast calculation we used the well-known formula Eq. (2.1) [45] on a ROI selected at the center area of the channel with an assumed uniform speed distribution.

3.2.6 In Vivo Experiments

We organized the in vivo experiments at the Behavioral Studies Unit of the Institute of Experimental Medicine (KOKI). Our model animals were mice (strain: C57BL6/J). The mouse was deeply anesthetized by 25 mg/kg xylazine and 125 mg/kg ketamine in 0.9% NaCl mixture. We fixed the head of the anesthetized mouse in a stereotaxic frame (Stoelting Inc, USA). We made a 1 cm long sagittal incision on the skull and we cleaned the surface with 3% H_2O_2 . Next we opened the skull with a high speed drill and made a 5x5 mm cranial window on the parietal part. Physiological saline solution was put on the brain and covered with a glass cover slip to prevent the drying of the tissue and to create a plain slide surface that is the best optically. This time we used an objective with 4x magnification resulting in an $\approx 4x3$ mm useful visible area on the brain surface.

3.3. Sample-in-the-Loop LSCI

As a continuation of our TVI-LSCI method, we started working on an online measurement system with a feedback-based optimization method both for CW and TVI based LSCI.

3.3.1 Hardware

For the processing unit, we chose a Raspberry Pi 4 Model B (Raspberry Pi (Trading) Limited, United Kingdom). This embedded system is a small, relatively cheap, easily accessible and practical computer. It has a Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @1.5GHz CPU. Our model had 4GB LPDDR4-3200 SDRAM. It was important that it has USB 3.0 ports as well that is the requirement for the camera we used (Basler acA2040-55um, Basler Vision Technologies, Germany). Another advantage is that it has a 40 pin GPIO header. Using this, we were able to combine the previously used data acquisition card and host computer with only the Raspberry Pi 4.

For our Sample-in-the-Loop system, I improved our previous measurement setup. Once again, it was built around Thorlabs platforms and parts. The base has an adjustable platform to set the distance between the object and the objective above to the focal distance. A sturdy vertical platform is fixed to the massive base platform through the adjustable platform. The microscope part is firmly fixed to the former. From top to bottom, it consists of the followings: the camera (Basler acA2040-55um, Basler Vision Technologies, Germany); a screwable module that enables precise Z-axis adjustments; two module both enabling very precise X and Y-axis adjustments with the joint between them holding the microscope; a AC254-150-A-ML achromatic doublet lens to help to achieve a diffraction-limited spot; spacing tubes; 2x infinity corrected objective NA=0.055, focal length 200 *mm* (Mitutoyo MPLANAPO2X, Mitutoyo Corporation, Japan). To ensure better stability, I fixed the laser illumination source to the vertical platform too. I soldered a new, $\lambda=660\text{ nm}$, 50 *mW* laser diode (ADL-66505TL, Arima Lasers, Taiwan). This laser diode is less powerful and emits visible red light which is safer to the eye and easier to work with. I mounted the diode into a thermally stabilized mount (LDM21, Thorlabs, Germany) that was driven by a Thorlabs TED200C temperature controller. This way we could set the exact temperature value of the mount setting even the PID controls, further improving laser stability, the time to reach such stable temperature and eliminating mode hopping. I also installed a half lens onto the laser diode to spread and

extend the illumination area. The laser driver in this setup was changed to an off-the-shelf one (LDP-VRM 01-12 CA, PicoLAS, Germany). It is important to note, that based on our initial examination with a digital oscilloscope (DS1022C, Rigol Technologies Inc., China), we defined the minimum pulse length limit to be $10 \mu\text{m}$. Further shortening the pulses significantly raises the ratio of rising and falling edges and increases transients to such an extent, where it drastically lowers the average intensity and incoherent light becomes a significant factor [46]. We used an optically black background cavity below the object (channel slide) to avoid unwanted background scattering. The schematics of the measurement setup, a custom developed channel slide and the assembled system can be seen on Fig. 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Measurement setup for Sample-in-the-Loop LSCI. Fig. a) outlines the operation procedure. [4] b) shows the custom developed microfluidic channel slide I designed. c) is an image of the system I helped to build.

3.3.2 Operation Procedure

We developed a custom software for the system. It directly takes the camera control, generates the desired pulsewave pattern and sends them to the laser driver controlling the illumination, and at the same time it triggers the camera to synchronously capture an image with the desired exposure time. All image post-processing is done by the software, which then tries to optimize the parameters for the next measurement based on the current results, see Fig. 3.4.

3.3.3 Laser Pulse Optimization

During our investigation we found, that conventional laser speckle imaging has a limitation where it is able to pick up only a short range of flow speeds that corresponds to only a relatively small portion of the physiologically relevant flow dynamics. MESI is a widely known method using multiple exposures to gather information across magnitudes of flow speeds [31]. We compressed the multi-exposure methods into a single-exposure method starting along [33], proposing a time varied illumination during LSCI, which was implemented with a pulsed coded laser illumination [3]. This method extended the dynamic range, and offered a solution to some of the problems with MESI. The pulsetrains consists of uniform intensity and uniform length discrete pulses with a variable duty cycle to mimic different average illumination intensities. However, the pulse pattern was either a non-optimal predefined one or a model-based one raising limitations. To address these limitations and to create a system with an automated environment for measurements, we need to optimize the laser pulse pattern algorithmically. We also noticed, that there might be scenarios, where the optimization goal was different, e.g. maximize sensitivity to a short range of flow speeds.

First we defined what parameters could be the variables of an optimization method. For a measurement the exposure time was given as such. As I already mentioned it in Section 3.2.2, to be able to capture flows of lower τ_c values, using the minimum – fixed – pulse length was given. The illumination intensity of the laser diode is also a function only of the hardware (non-collimated laser diode, lens) in our setup. Only one additional variable was defined to produce the discrete pulse sequence controlling the spacing between the consecutive pulses. After the initial high state, a power function determines the number of the following low states (n_{LOW}) is:

$$n_{LOW}(i) = \text{round}(i^\gamma) - 1, \quad (3.4)$$

where i is an index of the uniform (pulse)length binary states during a single exposure on the interval $i \in [0, \frac{T}{10\mu s}]$. γ is the spacing factor that determines the rate of pulse density decline. We set the practical limit as $\gamma \in [0, 1.4]$ considering the pulse width and the typical exposure times. Note, that the continuous wave operation mode is a special boundary case where $\gamma = 0$.

Finally, three main optimization goals were set in light of different measurement scenarios: contrast setpoint, where the user wants to achieve a desired average contrast value in a single ROI; sensitivity maximization, where the user wants to have maximum sensitivity between the flow maps of two selected ROIs; dynamic range maximization, which ultimately is a TVI-LSCI optimization scenario, where the user wants to maximize the dynamic range between two selected ROIs.

For the automated optimization it is important to take special cases into consideration as well. If the average intensity is too low (dark image) or too high (saturated image) during exposure, the speckle pattern will not be fully developed and the contrast calculation will yield heavily deviating, false values [47]. In the case of low brightness, the contrast values will be high and in the case of saturation, the contrast values will be too low (Fig. 3.5). In order to prevent these situations, we added a penalty term to the cost function of all three optimization problems. Below a predefined threshold, it linearly increases the cost as intensity decreases in the ROI. In our optimization cases although, saturation does not have to be explicitly handled, as it already increases the cost in all three cases. Due to the magnification and resolution, and the size of the cross section of our custom designed channel slide, we used 10x10 to 50x50 pixel size ROIs. All three optimization scenarios were defined as a cost minimization problem.

3.3.4 Contrast Setpoint Control

Choosing the contrast setpoint control mode, the user first defines the target contrast value. After adjusting the microscope and the object/slide, they select a ROI of the field of view. In this simple measurement scenario a continuous wave LSCI is used, and as such, there is no spacing variable to optimize. A gradient descent algorithm modifies

Figure 3.5: The calculated contrast of the ROI against the intensity. It depicts the experimentally defined threshold value of around 40 average intensity. [4]

the sole variable, the camera exposure time – in sync with the length of illumination. A single step in the gradient descent update is as follows:

$$T_{i+1} = T_i - \eta \frac{\Delta J}{\Delta T}, \quad (3.5)$$

where T_i is the exposure time of iteration i , η is a constant learning rate or step size, ΔJ and ΔT denotes the differences in cost J and exposure length between the i -th and $i - 1$ -th step respectively. The cost function was defined as:

$$J = |\kappa - \kappa_{ref}| + J_I, \quad (3.6)$$

where κ – for simplicity – is the average calculated contrast in the ROI, κ_{ref} is the previously defined desired contrast setpoint and J_I is the added penalty term for extreme intensities:

$$J_I = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \bar{I} \geq \bar{I}_{ref}, \\ \frac{\bar{I} - \bar{I}_{ref}}{\lambda}, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

where \bar{I} is the average, \bar{I}_{ref} is the predefined reference average intensity threshold of the ROI used. In order to normalize the difference between the threshold and the actual average intensity to the absolute contrast difference, an experimentally determined $\lambda = 40$ was set.

3.3.5 Sensitivity Maximization

Choosing the sensitivity maximization mode, the user first have to adjust the microscope and the object/slide, then they have to select two ROIs of the field of view. In this measurement scenario, once again, continuous wave LSCI was used, as we already showed that it has the highest sensitivity [3]. Similarly to the contrast setpoint mode, the camera exposure time is the sole variable parameter to maximize the sensitivity in this setup [40]. Once again, we used gradient descent optimization method defining the cost function as the inverse of the difference between the calculated contrast values of the two ROIs:

$$J = \frac{1}{|\kappa_1 - \kappa_2| + \epsilon} + J_I, \quad (3.8)$$

where κ_1 and κ_2 are the average contrast values in ROI(1) and ROI(2) respective, J_I is the intensity penalization term, and $\epsilon > 0$ is added to avoid division by zero.

3.3.6 Dynamic Range Maximization

Choosing the dynamic range maximization mode, the user first have to define a reference contrast value around which the sensitivity is ought to be the least. After adjusting the microscope and the object/slide, they have to select two ROIs of the field of view. In this measurement scenario however, we implemented time varied illumination during camera exposure to extend the dynamic range of laser speckle contrast imaging measurements [3]. This time, we used a grid search algorithm [48] as a tool for multivariate optimization. It was chosen over gradient descent because of the ease of implementation, stability and fast enough convergence. The cost function to be minimized was defined as the sum of differences of calculated average ROI values and the reference contrast value:

$$J = |\kappa_1 - \kappa_{ref}| + |\kappa_2 - \kappa_{ref}| + J_I, \quad (3.9)$$

where κ_{ref} is a user defined contrast value, around which the sensitivity is ought to be the least.

3.3.7 Designed Channel Slide

During the development of this system we needed a proper channel slide for constant performance monitoring and feedback. At first we selected and ordered a number of different rhombic, meander and continuous-flow microfluidic chips (Fluidic 134, Fluidic 708,

Fluidic 47 with product numbers 10000121, 10000753, 10000008; Microfluidic ChipShop, Germany). Initially we used them while developing the bases of the software and for contrast setpoint control, however, they have no high enough differences in flow speeds for sensitivity and dynamic range maximization evaluation. Other limitations were that we did not know the actual flow profiles, and the slides wore out and cracked rather quickly, probably due to the laser light. This raised the need for a custom designed, PDMS-on-glass channel slide. I designed the size and shape of the channels with several requirements in mind: i) most of the channel slide should fit in the field of view of our current setup; ii) there should be at least an order of magnitude different flow speeds visible in the slide; iii) both very different flow speeds and similar flow speeds should be next to each other, but in reverse flow directions. The channel slide design I created in AutoCAD 2020 [49] can be seen on Fig. 3.6.

Figure 3.6: The AutoCAD design of the custom developed channel slide. The annotated distances are in μm . [4]

For the manufacturing, first I ported the design to .cif format. Then I created the actual wafer layout of the channel design in CleWin layout designer software [50] also adding the actual inlets and outlets with the proper size. To be sure that the PDMS over the wider parts of the channels do not bend in or deform too much, I created a

design with one row of columns in the middle of the channel with widths of 500-1000 μm . The finalized wafer layout had 4 original and 4 columned channel slides of which one was manufactured with channel height of 100 μm . I also created a set of physics simulations in COMSOL Multiphysics [51] with both designs (with and without columns) modelling the flow of pure water and blood in the channels to have a general idea of the true flowspeeds. During experiments we used the original designs.

3.4. Ensemble Averaging Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging

Ensemble averaging or averaging in laser speckle contrast analysis means that a set of consecutive measurements are done and then the results are averaged to eliminate statistical uncertainties and so to correct for statistical error. Throughout this set of measurements, static scatterers are fixed (spatially and temporally) e.g. particles/contamination in the channel slide or the tissue around and above the blood vessels. The laser source is also thermally stable and fixed. This results in a visible frozen speckle pattern on the images meaning that the resulting image is granular where static scatterers are abundant which affects flow rate estimation on these areas. The traditional ensemble averaging method does not eliminate these static intensity patterns, because they can be considered as a systematic error. However, using interframe uncorrelated illumination and a sufficient number of measurements basically transforms this systematic error to a statistical one, creating true ensemble averaging, which ideally improves the estimation of true values $\propto 1/\sqrt{n}$ [52], [53]. We described the theory and mathematics behind, and proposed a statistical model of the effect of ensemble averaging in the case of stable illumination and interframe decorrelated illumination. We also investigated how the contrast map quality is improved as a function of the proportion of static and dynamic scatterers.

To achieve true ensemble averaging, we needed to maintain the properties of the traditional averaging while forcing the decorrelation of the static speckle pattern in a frame-by-frame manner. For that, the laser intensity, exposure time and the object should not change during exposure, the correlation time of the objective speckle pattern τ_I – that is the speckle pattern of the projected laser illumination – should be significantly larger than the exposure time: $\tau_{obj} \gg T$. Naturally, this decorrelation should be introduced to the entire ROI, with the above premises fulfilled.

Technical solutions for laser speckle reduction for other imaging cases as well as for ensemble averaging already exist. [52] proposed illuminating the object surface through a slowly rotating diffuser, which was ground glass in their case. [54] provides a step-by-step guide for such application. [55] uses an oscillating micromirror, which changes only the illumination angle while the laser spot remains almost fixed, creating new speckle patterns during a single exposure. [53] presents both diffuser-based and micromirror-based solutions for the related field digital image speckle correlation. A general speckle reduction technique designed for laser projection was introduced using a dynamic deformable mirror [56]. Other techniques that change the properties of the laser diode or the laser illumination might also be used in ensemble averaging: changing the wavelength [57] with tunable laser diodes [58], or changing the phase with spatial light modulators.

3.4.1 Effect of Ensemble Averaging on Static and Dynamic Scatterers

Even though I did not work on the modelling part of ensemble averaging, and only contributed indirectly, I describe our findings published in [5].

To model the effect of ensemble averaging and the effect of the number of samples averaged, we formulated the combination of static and dynamic scatterer intensity speckle patterns. For a single exposure, the static component is modeled as a frozen, non-changing fully developed speckle pattern, while the dynamic part is modeled as a temporarily integrated distribution [45]. An additional independent noise term was also added that was modeled with a Gaussian noise. The resulting formula is as follows:

$$I = (1 - \rho)S(\lambda_S) + \rho D(k_D, \lambda_D) + W, \quad (3.10)$$

where ρ and $(1 - \rho)$ are the fraction of dynamic to total scatterers and the fraction of static and total scatterers as usual, Static scatterers are described with random variables S of an exponential distribution with $\lambda_S > 0$ rate parameter. Dynamic scatterers are described with random variables D of a gamma distribution, with $k_D > 0$ shape parameter and $1/\Theta = \lambda_D > 0$ rate parameter. The noise term random variable of normal distribution $W \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_W, \sigma_W^2)$ takes the camera noise into account, where μ_W models the accumulated bias and σ_W^2 models the overall variance of systematic (offset) and random (zero-mean) noises such as dark current, readout, photon and other electronic noises.

We expressed a quality factor based on the variance and mean. There is no closed-form for the standard deviation of sample standard deviation, and approximating with

the Taylor series expansion – even the second order approximation – is highly inaccurate due to the high degree non-linearity of the problem. Hence, a variance based variable is defined by:

$$K_s^v = \frac{\sigma_s'^2}{\mu_s'}, \quad \epsilon_K^v = \frac{\text{Var}(K_s^v)}{\text{E}(K_s^v)}, \quad (3.11)$$

where $\sigma_s'^2$ is the sample variance and μ_s' is the sample mean. K_s^v is calculated on a spatial sliding window of $n_s \times n_s$ pixels similarly to the spatial speckle contrast calculation. ϵ_K^v is calculated through n frames.

To measure the effect of the number of samples, we used n for constructing variables both for stable and decorrelated illumination methods. We incorporated $n^{1/4}$ into the dependent variables. As the illumination in both cases does not modify the expected value, separate variables can be used for the variance and expected value calculation. Using the scaling property of the exponential, the gamma distribution, and the variance, a change of variables can be described for stable and decorrelated illumination:

Stable illumination:

$$\text{Var} : \quad \lambda'_S = \frac{\lambda_S}{1-\rho}, \quad \lambda'_D = \frac{\lambda_D}{\rho} n^{1/4}, \quad k'_D = k_D, \quad \mu'_W = \mu_W, \quad \sigma'_W = \frac{\sigma_W}{n^{1/4}}, \quad (3.12)$$

Decorrelated illumination:

$$\text{Var} : \quad \lambda'_S = \frac{\lambda_S}{1-\rho} n^{1/4}, \quad \lambda'_D = \frac{\lambda_D}{\rho} n^{1/4}, \quad k'_D = k_D, \quad \mu'_W = \frac{\mu_W}{n^{1/4}}, \quad \sigma'_W = \frac{\sigma_W}{n^{1/4}} \quad (3.13)$$

Illumination independent:

$$\text{E} : \quad \lambda'_S = \frac{\lambda_S}{1-\rho}, \quad \lambda'_D = \frac{\lambda_D}{\rho}, \quad k'_D = k_D, \quad \mu'_W = \mu_W, \quad \sigma'_W = \sigma_W, \quad (3.14)$$

where the λ'_S , λ'_D , k'_D , μ'_W and σ'_W are the transformed variables. The quality is expressed as a function of sample size using moment generating functions [59]:

$$M_S(x) = \frac{\lambda'_S}{\lambda'_S - x}, \quad M_D(x) = \left(\frac{\lambda'_D}{\lambda'_D - x} \right)^{k_D}, \quad M_W(x) = e^{\mu_W x + 0.5(\sigma'_W x)^2}, \quad (3.15)$$

where M is the moment generating function. The k -th moment and the sum of the random variables are defined as:

$$M_I = M_S(x)M_D(x)M_W(x), \quad (3.16)$$

$$E[I^k] = \left. \frac{d^k}{dx^k} M_I(x) \right|_{x=0}. \quad (3.17)$$

The variance and the mean of the ratio distribution can be approximated using Taylor series expansion [60]. Utilizing that the covariance of the sample variance and sample mean is:

$$\mathbb{E}\left(\frac{\sigma_s'^2}{\mu_s'}\right) \approx \frac{\mathbb{E}(\sigma_s'^2)}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')} - \frac{\text{Cov}(\sigma_s'^2, \mu_s')}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')^2} + \frac{\text{Var}(\mu_s') \mathbb{E}(\sigma_s'^2)}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')^3}, \quad (3.18)$$

$$\text{Var}\left(\frac{\sigma_s'^2}{\mu_s'}\right) \approx \frac{\text{Var}(\sigma_s'^2)}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')^2} + \frac{\mathbb{E}(\sigma_s'^2)^2 \text{Var}(\mu_s')}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')^4} - \frac{2 \text{Cov}(\sigma_s'^2, \mu_s') \mathbb{E}(\sigma_s'^2)}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')^3}, \quad (3.19)$$

$$\text{Cov}(\sigma_s'^2, \mu_s') = \frac{\mu_3'}{n_s^2}, \quad (3.20)$$

$$\text{Var}(\sigma_s'^2) = \frac{\mu_4'}{n_s^2} - \frac{n_s^2 - 3}{n_s^2 - 1} \frac{\sigma_s'^4}{n_s^2}, \quad (3.21)$$

$$\text{Var}(\mu_s') = \frac{\sigma_s'^2}{n_s^2}, \quad (3.22)$$

$$K_s = \mathbb{E}\left(\frac{\sigma_s'}{\mu_s'}\right) \approx \frac{\mathbb{E}(\sigma_s')}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')} - \frac{\text{Cov}(\sigma_s', \mu_s')}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')^2} + \frac{\text{Var}(\mu_s') \mathbb{E}(\sigma_s')}{\mathbb{E}(\mu_s')^3}, \quad (3.23)$$

$$\text{Cov}(\sigma_s', \mu_s') = \frac{\mu_3'}{2\sigma_s' n_s^2}, \quad (3.24)$$

where μ_3' , μ_4' are the 3rd and 4th central moment, and n_s^2 is the area size. Naturally, two boundary values are ($\rho = 0, 1$), that is when there are either only static or dynamic scatterers. Assuming $\lambda_S = \lambda_D = \lambda$ for stable illumination, the formula condenses to the following:

$$\lim_{\substack{k_D \rightarrow 1 \\ \sigma_W \rightarrow 0 \\ \rho \rightarrow 1 \\ \mu_W \rightarrow 0}} \epsilon_K^v = \frac{n_s^2 - 4n^{1/4}(n_s^2 - 1) + \sqrt{n}(8n_s^2 - 6) - 1}{\lambda n^{3/2}(n_s^2 - 1)^2}, \quad (3.25)$$

$$\lim_{\substack{k_D \rightarrow 1 \\ \sigma_W \rightarrow 0 \\ \rho \rightarrow 0 \\ \mu_W \rightarrow 0}} \epsilon_K^v = \frac{5n_s^2 - 3}{\lambda(n_s^2 - 1)^2}, \quad (3.26)$$

In Eq. (3.25), with stable illumination the quality factor of only dynamic scatterers improves with the increasing number of samples taken $\epsilon_K^v \propto 1/n$, which is the expected behavior. At the same time Eq. (3.26) shows, that with stable illumination the quality factor of only static scatterers does not increase the flatness of the calculated contrast maps. However, interframe decorrelated illumination reduces the variability of static scatterers too, as it makes the sample independent.

We implemented and conducted numerical simulations [61], [62] to validate and observe the results of our model on mixed static and dynamic objects. Fig. 3.7 shows the values

of quality factor ϵ_K^v against the ratio of dynamic scatterers ρ for both the numerical simulation and the model output in the case of stable and decorrelated illuminations, as well as the calculated spatial contrast. The four graphs show the effect of ensemble averaging with number of samples $n = 1, 2, 5, 100$.

Fig. 3.8 shows how changing the different parameters of the distribution affects the shape of the quality factor and spatial contrast curves against ρ . Naturally, increasing σ_W increases spatial contrast, as it adds variance to the speckle image. On the contrary, increasing μ_W mean noise level diminishes the contrast of the image. k_D shape parameter effects only the gamma distribution of dynamic scatterers, and it is related to the ratio of exposure time to decorrelation time, and so larger k_D corresponds to a blurred, decorrelated image.

Figure 3.7: A comparison of the numerical simulations and the model shows the values of quality factor ϵ_K^v against the ratio of dynamic scatterers ρ both in the case of stable and decorrelated illuminations, as well as the calculated spatial contrast. n denotes the number of samples averaged. The size of the sliding window was $n_s = 20$. For the numerical simulations based on [61], [62], we generated independent random samples for D and W variables keeping S variable constant. Parameters were chosen so that D and S had identical mean. The shape parameter was $k_D = 2$, resulting a $\sqrt{2}$ spatial contrast when $\rho = 1$. $\mu_W = 0$ and $\sigma_W = 0$ were set. Note, that quality factor ϵ_K^v is assigned to the left axis, and spatial contrast K_s is assigned to the right axis. A lower quality factor means less granulated, better contrast maps. [5]

Figure 3.8: The effect of model parameters on quality factor (dashed line) and spatial contrast (solid line). Each parameter was changed around an exemplary value based on the findings of ex vivo experiments. The arrows indicate the direction of increase in the denoted parameter. [5]

3.4.2 Ensemble Averaging for Temporal Speckle Contrast Imaging

We briefly inspected the case of temporal speckle contrast calculations [28] as well. This method based on Eq. (2.5) was already shown to be less exposed to the presence of static scatterers [32]. It calculates the flowrate based on the fluctuations of intensities across a number of consecutive laser speckle images taken over a short period of time. Applying interframe decorrelated illumination would introduce such heavy artifacts – by making the corresponding pixels on the individual frames statistically independent – that the measurement of flowrate would become impossible. However, decorrelation should be forced between the measurements to be averaged, and hence I proposed the following procedure: a complete temporal speckle laser contrast imaging measurement should be conducted, then another one with an independent objective speckle pattern (namely with decorrelated illumination) until enough contrast maps are calculated that can be accumulated and finally averaged for true ensemble averaging.

3.4.3 Practical Application and Experiments

To realize ensemble averaging, we modified our measurement system. Please note, that we worked on ensemble averaging after TVI-LSCI but before working on the Sample-in-the-Loop approach, and as such, the setup for ensemble averaging was a modified version of the one described in Section 3.2.4.

We modified our existing LSCI measurement system to include a pair of diffusers. To change the phase distribution of the objective speckle pattern from frame-to-frame realizing interframe decorrelated illumination, one of the diffusers were rotated during measurements (Fig. 3.9). Most previous diffuser-based solutions use only a single diffuser [52], [53], however the performance of doubly scattering systems for speckle reduction has already been discussed and shown to be superior. [63] and [64] evaluate the case of one moving and one static diffuser. A comprehensive comparison of different arrangements was also presented in [65]. A doubly scatterer arrangement has a number of advantages compared to single ones: the speckle patterns decorrelate faster, and when the two diffusers are close to each other, the required diffuser motion for decorrelation is of the order of the roughness correlation length of the diffuser. Moreover, a doubly scattered speckle system with mm range diameter aperture better approximates a Gaussian-distribution [66], [67]. Lastly, the theoretical maximum number of independent speckle patterns provided by a doubly scattering system is significantly larger than that of a single scattering system.

Figure 3.9: A doubly scattering system of diffusers changing the wavefront of the laser illumination.

For the laser illumination, we used a single-mode laser diode (RLD82PZJ2, $\lambda=820$ nm, 220 mW, ROHM Co., Ltd., Japan). As we did not need pulse modulation, the diode was driven by a simple and reliable RC model lipo battery. We mounted the diode into a TEC stage (LDM9T, Thorlabs, Newton, NJ, USA). This time the microscope part consisted of a 2x infinity-corrected objective with an $f=15$ cm tube lens and a linear polarizer (Thorlabs, Newton, NJ, USA). We used the same monochrome camera as previously. We used an optically black background cavity to avoid unwanted background scattering.

We used a pair of fused silica ground glass 1500 grit diffusers (DGUV10-1500, Thorlabs, Newton, NJ, USA) of which one was placed in a custom build rotating stage controlled by a DC servo motor. The resulting visible area was $4 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ with a speckle size $s \approx 10.4 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

We could not build our rotational diffuser stage to provide a stable exclusively inter-frame rotation, and so a constant rotational speed was chosen in such a manner, that decorrelation was fully developed interframe, but kept negligible intraframe. Optimal exposure times were chosen in the range of $2 - 3 \text{ ms}$ with 20 FPS resulting in 48 ms interframe times. We set the rotational speed to 0.05 rad/s to match $\tau_I \approx 50 \text{ ms}$ illumination decorrelation time with the interframe time. At the same time, during a single exposure the rotation induces decorrelation was negligible as $T_{exp}/\tau_I \approx 0.06$ [65]. The ensemble average setup is illustrated on Fig. 3.10.

Evaluation of the measurement and the effectiveness of ensemble averaging was done based on the spatiotemporal method [29]:

$$\epsilon_K = \frac{\sigma_K}{\mu_K}, \quad (3.27)$$

where ϵ_K quality factor is calculated from σ_K standard deviation and μ_K mean values of a region of interest of the spatial contrasts based on Eq. (2.1).

Figure 3.10: The ensemble average system. The measurement setup of the mouse brain surface is shown on the left side, while the ex vivo channel slide and leaf venation measurement arrangements are shown on the right side. [5]

We conducted three different experiments using ensemble averaging ex vivo and in vivo:

- For evaluation and validation purposes, a channel slide experiment was done using SMOFLipid intralipid emulsion (Fresenius Kabi AB, Uppsala, Sweden). The channel slide was covered with a series of different thickness diffusers to manipulate *rho*.
- The blood flow on the brain surface was measured through a cranial window of a mouse.
- Flow in the venation of a fresh *Ficus benjamina* leaf was examined.

4. Results

In this chapter I describe the results of my work and the related results. First I show the results in TVI-LSCI: how we did model identification, optimized the pulse modulation pattern offline, then how we applied it in ex vivo and in vivo experiments. These results were published in [3]. Second, I share details about the implemented software, then I show the ex vivo Sample-in-the-Loop optimization results of setpoint control, sensitivity maximization and dynamic range maximization scenarios. These results were published in [5]. Third, I give the results of ex vivo validation measurements regarding our model of improvement for ensemble averaging, then I introduce our results of an in vivo and ex vivo exemplary measurement. These results are submitted for publication in [4]. Finally, I discuss some shortcomings of our results, and I mention my other related works related in short.

4.1. TVI-LSCI

4.1.1 Model Identification

To mathematically describe TVI-LSCI from the underlying data and model the physics behind, we first identified Eq. (3.3) based on the ex vivo measurements (see Section 3.2.5). In the followings, for simplicity, we assumed the general case of single scattering unordered motion and multiple scattering ordered motion regimes, where the variable based on the second order dynamics is $n = 1$. We defined the relation between correlation time τ_c and v flow speed in a channel slide as:

$$\tau_c := k \frac{1}{v + v_b}, \quad (4.1)$$

where k is a scaling factor, and we assumed $\rho = 1$. We added the term v_b as the speed of Brownian motion. As [31] proposed Eq. (3.3) was extended with offset v_s accounting for static scatterers and measurement noise. We defined a minimum optimization problem to minimize the root-mean-square error (RMSE) of the measured and simulated contrast values with free parameters β , k , v_s and v_b :

$$\min_{\beta, k, v_b, v_s} \sum_{i=1}^N RMSE(\kappa^{(i)} - \kappa_{sim}^{(i)}), \quad (4.2)$$

where N is the number of different exposure times, κ is the measured and κ_{sim} is the simulated contrast. We implemented and conducted the optimization problem in MATLAB

2020a [43] using its default interior-point method of its *fmincon* function. We generated 20 initial points using Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) method [68]. The parameters identified are $\beta = 0.195$, $k = 6.027 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ mm}$ and $v_b = 0.0072 \text{ mm/s}$. The resulting error was $RMSE = 0.012 \pm 0.0047$.

4.1.2 Pulse Modulation Optimization

After model identification, we used the results to create an optimized pulsed illumination profile to use in further ex vivo and in vivo measurements. We had to formulate mathematically the optimization problem such that it leads to the best extension of the dynamic range of the traditional laser speckle contrast imaging shown in Fig. 3.1. We defined the time varied intensity pulsed modulation profile as such, that a single exposure to have a number of sections. Each section had a continuous wave illumination assigned with different intensities in a decreasing manner, that are constant in a single section. Then these sections were transformed to pulse coded illumination patterns with average intensities corresponding to the continuous wave illumination counterparts. In a section the spacing between the pulses are equal. As the length of a section was not fixed, there were two free parameters per section to be optimized: the section length and the duty cycle of the pulsetrains. The pulses had constant intensity – the inherent intensity of the laser diode – and constant width $T_{on} = 5 \mu s$ – the minimum feasible pulse width limited by the hardware. Due to the fixed minimum pulse length, section length T_i must be integer divisible with T_{on} without remainder, and as such section length in practice becomes $T_i = \text{round}\left(\frac{N_i T_{on}}{1 - D_i}\right)$, where N_i is the number of pulses in a section and D_i is the duty cycle.

Because of the rounding, this time we could not use the gradient-based optimization method *fmincon*, which needs continuous functions. Instead, we chose the *patternsearch* algorithm of MATLAB. Once again, it was applied to 20 initial points generated with LHS method. We defined the cost function with restrains as the followings:

$$\min_{T_i, D_i} \sigma\left(\frac{\Delta\kappa(T, \tau_c)}{\Delta t_c}\right) + \mu\left(\frac{\Delta\kappa(T, \tau_c)}{\Delta t_c}\right)^{-1}, \quad (4.3)$$

$$\text{subject to } t_c = \log(\tau_c), \quad (4.4)$$

$$\sum_i T_i \cdot D_i = T_{const}, \quad (4.5)$$

where there are two constrains: Eq. (4.4) is a change of variables as our goal is to achieve a near-linear flow mapping to contrast on the logarithmic scale; (4.5) is a constrain on

exposure time, where T_{const} is the total laser on time of the equivalent exposure using one constant frequency. In Eq. (4.3) $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the standard deviation, which optimized towards a minimum forces a constant on the difference quotients, meaning that it forces a linear-like response on the contrast to logarithm of correlation time relation. $\mu(\cdot)$ is the mean, taking its inverse means that during optimization we want to maximize the mean of difference quotients on the logarithmic scale, essentially maximizing the slope/gradient of said linear-like response extending the contrast values covered.

The result of simulation and the measured speckle variances are shown in Fig. 4.1. Due to the limitations of our setup, we emulated continuous wave illumination with uniformly distributed pulse train illumination (UDP) that was already a proven method [39]. UDP is shown with 5 different exposure times ranging from 2 to 20 *ms*, while TVI method had 5 *ms* exposure time. Each curve is a single exposure to correlation time simulation. Dots of different colors are measurements of different exposure times at sampling points on the correlation time axis. The result demonstrates that the TVI method indeed extends the correlation time – and hence the flow rate – range covered in a single exposure, as it was expected.

Figure 4.1: A comparison of speckle variances with continuous wave-like illumination emulated with uniformly distributed pulse trains (UDP) and time varied illumination (TVI). a) The contrast results of the two illumination methods with a number of exposure times, plotted against correlation time. Lines represent the simulated, dots represent the measured results. TVI indeed shows an extended dynamic range. Note, that x-axis uses a logarithmic scale. [3] b) Illustration of UDP and TVI pulsetrains. Note that for UDP, only a section of the pulse trains (1000 μs) is shown for visualization reasons. [3]

4.1.3 In Vivo Experiment Results

We conducted in vivo experiments in accordance with Section 3.2.6 to evaluate our TVI-LSCI method and our ex vivo optimized pulse modulation profile on realistic use cases as well. After the animal has been anesthetized, and the cranial window has been prepared, we adjusted the setup. For each measurement we captured a sequence of 100 frames. We calculated contrast on each using a 7×7 pixels sliding window with Eq. (2.1). To decrease statistical errors, we averaged over the resulting 100 contrast maps which resulted in a single contrast map – with improved signal-to-noise ratio – for each measurement. A number of measurements were done using both continuous illumination and pulse modulated illumination methods.

Fig. 4.9 shows the results of the in vivo measurements. It can be seen, that in this case, TVI-LSCI performs similarly to conventional CW LSCI. This can be explained, that – in accordance with the simulations and previous measurements – the brain surface of a mouse does not have such high range of flow speeds that would validate the need for an extended dynamic range. Unfortunately, we could not conduct in vivo experiments with high flow speed ranges such that can be found e.g. in the human blood vessels.

Figure 4.2: Averaged measurement results of the in vivo experiment showing false color contrast images of the same area using conventional continuous LSCI (CW 5 ms) and time varied illumination LSCI (TVI 5 ms) of 5 ms exposure times. The shown field of view is $3.2 \times 3.2 \text{ mm}^2$. Arbitrarily chosen ROIs with different flow speeds were chosen. On the right side, we compare the calculated contrast values on a sequence of ROIs marked on the left side images both with CW illumination and TVI. It can be seen, that on this flow speed range CW and TVI methods show similar characteristics. [3]

4.2. Sample-in-the-Loop

4.2.1 Software

I took a major part in the implementation of the Sample-in-the-Loop LSCI software. We used Qt Creator [69] development environment in C++ 11 programming language under Raspberry Pi OS. We used Basler's Pylon SDK for camera handling. We used OpenCV 4.5.1-dev [70] open source computer vision library for image processing. The nlopt library [48] was used to implement the grid search optimization. The PiGPIO library [71] is used to handle the GPIO pins of the Raspberry Pi, namely to generate the camera trigger signal, the pulses of the illumination pattern, and to send them to the camera and laser driver.

The software is approximately 1500 lines long. It has a .pro file that is the qmake descriptor file. Beside the main.cpp file, there are three classes with header and sources run on three threads utilizing QThread: mainclass, optimizer and videocamera. The mainclass class has every setting, and it instantiates the other two classes. It is responsible for pulse generation through GPIO using PiGPIO. The videocamera class handles the camera, taking 10 images to be averaged when called to reduce noise and improve the consistency of the optimization. Finally, the optimizer is responsible for the image processing and the optimization process. The operation is as follows: optimization goal, parameters and initial variables are set by the mainclass class, which instantiates the videocamera and optimizer classes. A single initial speckle image is taken, which is shown to the user. The user selects the ROI or ROIs, depending on the measurement scenario. Then the mainclass sends the trigger signal to the videocamera class which takes a set of images (10 images), and at the same time in sync with the camera trigger, the mainclass sends the pulsetrains to the laser driver. Once image acquisition has finished, the optimizer processes and averages the images. Then the optimizer sets the variables for the next measurement based on the calculated cost and optimization goal. The software continues with the next iteration until i) the optimization has converged to a minimum or ii) the maximum number of iterations is reached.

To evaluate the system and demonstrate the different optimization goals, we conducted a number of ex vivo experiments, using the custom developed channel slide. A syringe pump drove intralipid emulsion through the channel slide similarly to the experiment described in Section 3.2.5.

4.2.2 Contrast Setpoint Control

To demonstrate a contrast setpoint control scenario, once the optimization goal was selected, we set a desired 0.2 reference contrast value. After adjusting the optical system and the channel slide, we selected a single ROI. The initial calculated contrast value was 0.27 with a predefined exposure time of 3 ms. Figure 4.3 shows how the exposure length and contrast changes in each iteration during the run of the algorithm. After starting the optimization, we kept the flow speed in the ROI constant, and the algorithm settled after around 17 iterations, when it found an optimum of ≈ 6.1 ms exposure time to achieve the reference contrast value. At iteration 50, we increased the flow speed which resulted in the contrast value dropping to 0.16. Shortly after the algorithm was able to compensate by around iteration number 65 achieving the desired 0.2 contrast with ≈ 4.2 ms exposure time. The fluctuation of the exposure time and contrast is due to the measurement noises and the constant step size of the optimization.

Figure 4.3: The exposure times and calculated contrast values of the ROI in each iteration (sample number) during the experiment. The constant flow speed was increased once, marked with a red dashed line. The reference contrast value is marked with a green dashed line.[4]

4.2.3 Sensitivity Maximization

Sensitivity Maximization can be achieved using continuous wave illumination changing only the exposure time (and intensity), however, to further demonstrate the difference between CW illuminated LSCI and TVI-LSCI, conducted an experiment where the optimization algorithm (grid search) and parameters (spacing factor and exposure time) were that of dynamic range maximization (see Section 3.3.6) using the cost function of sensitivity maximization.

Fig. 4.4 shows that – as it is expected – decreasing the spacing factor, that is approximating continuous wave illumination, decreases the cost with a variance introduced likely by measurement uncertainty. An optimum was found with exposure time of ≈ 4.1 ms and spacing factor $\gamma = 0.11$.

Figure 4.4: The relation of cost against spacing factor and exposure time. The lowest costs are achieved when the spacing factor is close to 0 which corresponds to continuous wave illumination. [4]

4.2.4 Dynamic Range Maximization

Our Sample-in-the-Loop implementation of dynamic range maximization uses the grid search algorithm [48], with the goal to minimize the cost function Eq. (3.9), see Section 3.3.6. Fig. 4.5 shows that the algorithm – minimizing cost – converges to a found minimum with spacing factor $\gamma = 0.31$ and exposure length 0.8 ms. Note, that it can be seen that using time varied illumination the cost can be decreased.

Figure 4.5: Cost values in respect with spacing factor and exposure length. The results show a decreased cost in case of TVI-LSCI compared to CW illumination LSCI. [4]

As a proof of concept, we visualized the whole cost surface with respect to the spacing factor and exposure length. A number of measurements were done with different parameter values sampled in the practically relevant ranges: spacing factor from 0 to 1.4 and exposure times from 1 *ms* to 30 *ms*. Two set of measurements were done with 0.1 and 0.3 reference contrast value. For demonstration purposes, cost (Eq. (3.9)) was calculated both without and with the intensity penalization term (Eq. (3.7)).

Fig. 4.6 shows the resulting cost surfaces, where the black circles mark the found minima. The left-side figures show the "raw", unpenalized cost values. It can be observed, that the cost values are driven by extreme average intensity values in the two extrema of the spacing factor range: i) saturation when the spacing factor is low and ii) underexposure when the spacing factor is high. The first case means that the illumination converges to continuous wave illumination, which results in overexposed, saturated images when the exposure time is high enough, and the contrast diminishes. The second case means that the pulse modulated intensity decreases so rapidly, that the camera noise and every non-zero pixel introduces numerical instability which falsely translates to a high contrast, yet again increasing the cost. As our concern was the second case, we added a linear penalization term for underexposure defined by a threshold preset. The right-side figures of Fig. 4.6 show the expanded costs and so the effect of the penalization term. Naturally, reaching the threshold depends both on the spacing factor and the exposure length.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.6: Cost surface covered by a set of measurements. Cost values without intensity penalization term are shown on the left side, total costs are shown on the right side with respect to spacing factor and different exposure times. The reference contrast value was set on subplot a) as $\kappa_{ref} = 0.1$, an on subplot b) as $\kappa_{ref} = 0.3$. [4]

4.3. Ensemble Averaging

We conducted three different experiments with the setup described in Section 3.4.3. First, a channel slide experiment with known flow speeds was done, where we changed ρ in order to evaluate and validate our model of ensemble averaging. Second, we conducted two real-life experiments: an in vivo experiment measuring the blood flow of the brain surface of a mouse; and an ex vivo experiment measuring the flow in the venation of a fresh leaf.

4.3.1 Channel Slide Experiment

In the channel slide measurements, the syringe pump (SN-50F6, Sino Medical-Device Technology Co., Ltd., China) drove a 10% intralipid emulsion in the μ -Slide I Luer channel slide of 200 μm channel height (ibidi GmbH, Germany) at a constant 2.0 mm/s speed. We used Scotch tape (Scotch Magic Tape, 3M, USA) as a weak diffuser to introduce a higher portion of static scatterers to the object. For a single measurement, we recorded 100 consecutive frames both without and with decorrelated illumination. The exposure time was set to 3 ms. For the speckle contrast calculation using Eq. 2.1 we used a sliding window of $n_s \times n_s = 7 \times 7$ pixels. Ensemble averaging was done by averaging through a number of frames, up to the total of 100 frames of stable illumination and 100 frames of decorrelated illumination as well. We calculated the non-uniformity of the contrast maps with Eq. 3.27 using a sliding window of $n_s \times n_s = 11 \times 11$ pixels.

To demonstrate the ρ -dependence of the method, we did 10 measurements of different thickness of the weak diffuser covering the channel slide. In the first measurement, there was no layer of diffuser applied to the channel slide, then in each consecutive measurement we added an additional layer of $\approx 54\mu\text{m}$ thickness covering the whole slide up to 9 final layers. For $\rho = 0$ we measured on a ground glass diffuser.

Fig. 4.7 shows that with stable illumination averaging (Fig. a)), the quality factor improvement heavily diminishes, while in the case of decorrelated illumination (Fig. b)), ensemble averaging provides a significant contrast map improvement. We can observe an interesting phenomenon, namely that the improvement of ground glass diffuser measurement series using decorrelated illumination is an outlier showing the ideal improvement rate of $\propto 1/\sqrt{n}$. This can be explained as the measured improvement using the quality factor is actually disturbed by structured surface patterns, which is practically negli-

Figure 4.7: Ensemble averaging improvement as a function of quality factor $\epsilon_K = \frac{\sigma_K}{\mu_K}$ and ρ . Fig. a) shows the improvement using the control measurements with stable illumination, while Fig. b) shows the results with decorrelated illumination. Fig. c) shows that the mean spatial contrast remains the same using decorrelated illumination ensemble averaging. [5]

ble in the case of the fine ground glass diffuser. Fig. 4.7c) shows a comparison of the calculated average contrast values in the case of stable illumination and decorrelated illumination ensemble averaging. The equal values of the results prove that the type of illumination does not affect the mean of the calculated spatial contrast values, however the contrast maps become less granulated.

We used the channel slide measurements to validate our model – given in Eqs.(3.11)-(3.22) – by comparing it to the result of an identification process. First we assumed, that i) we have measurements of boundary values $\rho = 0$ and $\rho = 1$, and ii) that each layer of the weak diffuser represents a constant $\Delta\rho$ value. This premise is illustrated in Fig. 4.8. Next, – among other model parameters – we identified $\Delta\rho$ parameter based on:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{\substack{\Delta\rho, \lambda_D, \lambda_S, \\ k_D, \mu_W, \sigma_W}} \frac{\sum_{n \in \{1, 100\}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_\rho} \sum_{k=1}^{n_\rho} (\Delta\epsilon_K^v(n))^2}}{2\epsilon_{K, max}^v} + \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n_\rho} \sum_{k=1}^{n_\rho} \Delta K_s^2}}{K_{s, max}} \\
 & \text{s.t.} \quad \rho = [0, 1 - k\Delta\rho], \\
 & \quad \quad k \in (0, 9) \subset \mathbb{Z}, \\
 & \quad \quad k_D \geq 1,
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.6}$$

where $n_\rho = 11$ is the number of measurement sets, $\Delta\epsilon_K^v$ is difference between the simulated and measured quality factor, and ΔK_s is the difference between the spatial contrasts. Furthermore, the quality factors are evaluated at the two extremes ($n = 1$ or $n = 100$), the contributions from the quality factor and spatial contrast are normalized by their maximum values $\epsilon_{K, max}^v$ and $K_{s, max}$, respectively. The modeled and measured

results fit well as it can be seen in Fig. 4.8.

Figure 4.8: The identified and measured spatial spatial contrasts and quality factors. $\Delta\rho = 0.08$, $\lambda_S = 0.0042$, $\lambda_D = 0.01$, $k_D = 17$, $\mu_W = 0.0015$, $\sigma_W = 0.0016$. [5]

4.3.2 Mouse Cranial Window Experiment

During the in vivo experiment, a cranial window of a deeply anesthetized mouse was prepared for measurement with the same protocol described in Section 3.2.6. We set the exposure time to 3 ms to achieve a proper mean image intensity level. Just as before, we recorded a sequence of 100 frames using stable illumination and 100 frames using decorrelated illumination for comparison. The spatial window of contrast calculation was $n_s \times n_s = 7 \times 7$ pixels. Finally, the contrast maps were averaged. Fig. 4.9a) shows the brightfield image of the cranial window. Figure b) is the averaged stable illumination speckle contrast map and Fig. c) is the averaged decorrelated illumination speckle contrast map. Figure d) shows the averaged spatial contrasts along the marked lines of cross-sections 1 and 2.

Despite the fact that the difference between the resulted images are not spectacular, a significant quality factor improvement can be observed. The extent of the improvement varies based on the different areas. After comparing to the brightfield image, the following areas can be distinguished along the cross-section: decorrelated illumination ensemble averaging yielded a 45 – 50% lower ϵ_K for the partially tissue-covered region, 15 – 20% lower ϵ_K for parenchyma, and 10 – 15% lower ϵ_K for larger vessels. Note, that the structured nature of the imaged surface has a significant effect on the rate of improvement calculated with our quality metric contributing to the differences between the named areas.

Figure 4.9: Fig. a) brightfield image of the mouse cranial window. Fig. b) averaged stable illumination contrast map. Fig. c) averaged decorrelated illumination contrast map. Fig. d) contrast values along the marked lines of cross-section 1 and 2 of 3 mm length. [5]

4.3.3 Leaf Venation Experiment

I proposed a method of ensemble averaging with decorrelated illumination for temporal speckle contrast analysis in Section 3.4.2. We found the measurement of the underside of a fresh *Ficus benjamina* leaf a good exemplary experiment, as both xylem and phloem flow velocities in the leaves are just below 1 mm/s , and such slow rates require temporal speckle contrast analysis instead of spatial [72]. This time, we set the exposure time to 10 ms . First, the control measurement of stable illumination was done, acquiring 5×20 frames with 20 FPS. On each 20-frame-long section temporal speckle contrast was calculated and then the 5 contrast maps averaged. During the decorrelated illumination ensemble average measurement, we took 100 frames in a similar manner, however, the rotational diffuser was rotated after each 20-frame-long section. We calculated temporal speckle contrast on each section and then averaged the resulting 5 contrast maps. Fig. 4.10a),b) and c) shows the brightfield image, stable illumination averaged temporal speckle contrast map and decorrelated illumination averaged temporal speckle contrast map respectively. The reduced granularity can be easily seen. Figure d) shows the temporal contrasts along the marked lines of the cross-sections. The difference in the variation

of the contrast is noticeable. Figure e) and f) shows the improvement of the quality factor at the marked areas with respect to the number of frames averaged in the case of stable and decorrelated illumination respectively. Note the different dependencies on dynamic scatter ratio.

Fig. 4.10 illustrates the viability and validity of (partial) ensemble averaging in the temporal speckle contrast domain. However, further investigations and the mapping of the limitations of the technique (e.g. ergodicity near static scatterers [73]) are needed.

Figure 4.10: Temporal speckle contrast measurement of the underside of a fresh *Ficus benjamina* leaf. a) brightfield image, b) stable illumination temporal contrast map, c) averaged temporal contrast map of 5×20 images, d) temporal contrast values along the marked cross-sections e-f) Improvement of the different marked areas as a function of quality factor to the number of frames averaged in the case of stable and decorrelated illumination. The cross-section is $\approx 1.7 \text{ mm}$ long. [5]

4.4. Discussion

Although we conducted an *in vivo* TVI-LSCI experiment, its results were not conclusive, as the brain surface of a mouse does not have high enough range of flow speeds to validate the use of TVI-LSCI. For that, we would need to arrange new *in vivo* experiments of high flow speed range found e.g. in the human circulatory system. The Sample-in-the-Loop implementation could be improved in a number of ways, for example incorporating a decaying stepsize, and including duty cycle optimization to achieve the best average intensity for CW measurements.

I have also took part in failed feasibility measurements to determine the flow direction field in microfluidic channels based on phase changes, which is not in the scope of this thesis. In addition, I implemented a speckle pattern generation script in MATLAB, which was later not used. I conducted initial measurements on the bioactivity of a fresh Ficus benjamina leaf and a damaged peach using a number of well-known biospeckle methods implemented in MATLAB preparing for future possible research in the field.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Evaluation of the Tasks Performed

I researched the related literature and works in the field of laser speckle imaging with a focus on laser speckle contrast imaging. I gained a deep understanding and comprehensive knowledge in the topic. I helped creating a camera system for Laser Speckle Imaging. I helped designing and creating a laser driver for our first measurement setup. I not only took part in the research and development of Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging, but I am a co-author of two published [3], [5] and one submitted scientific articles [4] about our methods improving the technique.

We proposed a new method called Time Varied Illumination Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging (TVI-LSCI) to increase the dynamic range of LSCI.. I took part in researching the theoretical background. I built the ex vivo experiment assembly. I organized the ex vivo measurements and took part in both the ex vivo and in vivo experiments. I helped evaluating the collected data and took part in writing the scientific article [3].

I helped defining the theoretical background of ensemble averaging laser speckle contrast imaging with decorrelated interframe illumination, which helps smoothing out the static scatterers induced granularity of the contrast maps. We proposed a model of improvement as a function of static scatterers. I helped building the measurement setup, and I proposed an experiment for the validation and a method to apply ensemble averaging on temporal speckle contrast imaging. I took part in writing the scientific article [5].

We proposed a feedback-based online optimization environment for Laser Speckle Contrast Imaging. I took part in defining three different optimization scenarios: contrast setpoint control, sensitivity maximization, and dynamic range maximization applying TVI-LSCI. I built the embedded system assembly for this Sample-in-the-Loop approach. I took a major role in implementing and developing the software. I designed a microfluidic channel slide phantom for flowmetry and system evaluation, and took part in conducting a number of ex vivo experiments. I took part in writing the submitted scientific article [4].

5.2. Future Possibilities

We are currently working on a new method to compensate saturation induced distortion of LSCI measurements. At the same time, we are planning to research and evaluate the various biospeckle methods. I have already conducted initial measurements on the bioactivity of a fresh *Ficus benjamina* leaf and a damaged peach using a number of well-known biospeckle methods implemented in MATLAB.

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A. Appendix

Sample-in-the-Loop The source code of our sample-in-the-loop software is available at the following link: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1C78tQw26Q6qu2Jloj84nPGGMae2V9/view?usp=sharing>

The software was developed and tested with the following dependencies:

- Qt Creator 4.8.2 with Qt 5.11.3 (GCC 8.3.0, 32bit) [69]
- OpenCV 4.5.1-dev [70]
- nlopt Version 2.6.2 [48]
- pylon 6.3.0 Camera Software Suite Linux x86 (64 Bit) [74]
- PiGPIO [71]
- Raspberry Pi OS - Raspbian GNU/Linux 10 (buster)